

EXPLORING SELF-DISCIPLINE AND SELF-MOTIVATION AMONG INCARCERATED STUDENTS IN DISTANCE E-LEARNING PROGRAMS

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ABSTRACT

This study, titled "Exploring Self-Discipline and Self-Motivation Among Incarcerated Students in Distance E-Learning Programs," was conducted in a Namibian correctional institution. Data were collected from 12 incarcerated students using audio-recorded interviews. Participants were selected based on their engagement in research while incarcerated. Following the transcription of the recorded data by a professional transcriber, the researcher analysed the content through an interpretive framework, employing the insights of other scholars to deepen the comprehension of participants' experiences related to self-discipline and self-motivation in distance e-learning contexts.

Keywords: Self-Discipline, Self-Motivation, Distance E-Learning, Qualitative Research

1. INTRODUCTION

This study explores the degrees of self-discipline and self-motivation in jailed students engaged in distance e-learning programs. The objective is to investigate the aspects that impact their academic engagement and achievement, thereby clarifying how these personal attributes influence their learning experiences and results. The research, conducted in a Namibian jail, involved twelve detained students, offering a concentrated analysis of this distinctive educational environment. Under the Namibian Correctional Service Regulations (Government Notice 331 of 2013, section 264 subsection 1), inmates permitted to engage in study may encounter repercussions if they abuse that privilege or their educational resources. Individuals restricted under sections 87 or 103 of the Act, or those who contravene established study requirements, may have their access to educational resources suspended, either temporarily or permanently [1]. This regulatory structure underscores the vital importance of self-discipline and self-motivation, which are crucial not just for academic achievement but also for preserving access to educational programs for jailed individuals. [2] found that self-discipline and self-motivation on incarcerated students' performance in their studies can serve as mediating factors for their behavior in their studies.

The primary research question for this project is: “In what ways do self-discipline and self-motivation affect the academic engagement and success of incarcerated students involved in distance e-learning programs?” This study aims to elucidate the correlation between individual characteristics and academic performance in a demanding context. The research will utilise qualitative and quantitative analyses to investigate the manifestation of self-discipline in students' study habits and time management, while also evaluating the role of self-motivation in their pursuit of success despite contextual limitations. Comprehending these processes may enhance the creation of more successful educational programs customised for jailed students, thereby facilitating their rehabilitation and reintegration into society.

1.1 PURPOSE

The purpose of this study is to investigate the levels of self-discipline and self-motivation among incarcerated students participating in distance e-learning programs. By understanding the factors that contribute to their academic engagement and success, the research aims to provide insights into how these qualities affect their learning experiences and outcomes.

1.2 RESEARCH QUESTION

How do self-discipline and self-motivation influence the academic engagement and success of incarcerated students participating in distance e-learning programs?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Self-Discipline and Self-Motivation Among Incarcerated Students in Distance E-Learning Programs

Despite existing research on discipline and motivation related to performance, a gap remains in understanding how these factors interact within the specific context of prison setting. Although discipline and motivation are recognised as critical factors, no comprehensive study has examined their simultaneous influence on incarcerated students' performance in a prison context [3].

The shift to online education has presented distinct difficulties and opportunities for jailed students. This group frequently encounters obstacles to education that surpass conventional academic difficulties, such as restricted access to technology, insufficient social interaction, and the psychological effects of incarceration [4]. Comprehending the functions of self-discipline and self-motivation in these situations is essential for formulating effective e-learning solutions customised to their requirements. Self-discipline is essential for success in any educational environment, especially in distance e-learning programs where conventional support networks

are frequently lacking. Incarcerated students may experience difficulties with self-regulation due to the environmental stressors inherent in prison life, such as isolation and institutional control [5]. A study by [6] revealed that jailed students exhibiting elevated self-discipline were more inclined to complete their online courses, as they effectively managed their time and resisted distractions. Furthermore, self-discipline can be developed through organised programs that establish explicit expectations and accountability. Institutions that implement regular evaluations and progress assessments can assist jailed students in establishing routines that promote self-discipline [7].

Self-motivation is crucial, especially in remote learning where external incentives may be scarce. Incarcerated individuals frequently seek education for personal growth or as a route to enhanced opportunities after release [4]. [8] assert that intrinsic motivation, fueled by personal objectives and a pursuit of self-improvement, can markedly increase participation in e-learning. A participant in their study remarked, "I seek knowledge not merely for the diploma but to enhance my character." Establishing a conducive educational atmosphere that prioritises individual objectives and applicability to real-world contexts might augment self-motivation among jailed learners. Programs that link course material to essential reintegration skills, such as job preparation and interpersonal communication, can enhance motivation for learning engagement [7]. Incarcerated students encounter significant obstacles regarding self-discipline and self-motivation, despite their relevance. Restricted access to resources, such as technology and educational materials, can impede their capacity to participate completely in distance learning [5]. Moreover, the psychological repercussions of imprisonment, including anxiety and sadness, might diminish students' motivation and self-discipline [6].

To tackle these problems, educational programs must adopt tactics that cultivate self-discipline and self-motivation. Facilitating access to technology and training can enable students to assume responsibility for their education. Additionally, integrating peer support systems that allow students to exchange experiences and strategies may improve motivation and accountability [4]. (Self-discipline is the capacity to regulate one's emotions, behaviours, and wants in response to external pressures, whereas self-motivation denotes the intrinsic impetus to pursue goal attainment [9]. Both are essential for success in remote e-learning, especially in correctional environments where conventional support systems are frequently deficient.

The individual objectives of jailed students may influence their motivation levels. Studies indicate that students with explicit, achievable goals tend to demonstrate increased self-discipline and commitment [10]. Students seeking to obtain skills for job post-release are likely to maintain motivation throughout their school. Programs that integrate goal-setting strategies may improve inmates' involvement in their academics. Peer and instructor support can develop a sense of community, essential for sustaining motivation. Research demonstrates that prisoners engaged in collaborative learning settings generally show heightened motivation and discipline [11]. Distance learning systems that include online discussion forums can assist inmates in connecting with others, sharing experiences, and offering mutual support.

Initiatives like Purdue University Global illustrate how organised support can improve self-discipline and motivation among jailed students. These programs, by offering extensive resources such as academic advising and mentorship, have demonstrated superior completion rates relative to traditional models [12]. Furthermore, integrating technology training into the curriculum has enhanced inmates' confidence and self-efficacy in overseeing their education. Notwithstanding the prospective advantages of remote e-learning for jailed individuals, numerous problems endure. The absence of reliable access to technology and educational resources might impede advancement. Furthermore, the jail setting frequently enforces limitations that may dissuade students from motivation. It is advisable for correctional institutions to partner with educational organisations to provide customised programs that account for the specific needs of jailed learners. Implementing strategies including flexible course frameworks, improving resource accessibility, and cultivating a supportive learning community can markedly enhance self-discipline and motivation [13].

2.2 Self-Discipline in Distance Learning

[14] believe that discipline can have a positive influence on student performance, meaning that the discipline applied can improve their performance. Self-discipline in remote learning refers to students' capacity to govern their behaviour, efficiently manage their time, and maintain concentration on academic activities in the absence of direct supervision from instructors [15]. [16] posits that self-regulated learning, encompassing self-discipline, entails goal formulation, self-monitoring, and self-reflection. These qualities are essential for students confronting the difficulties of online learning environments. This corresponds with the self-determination hypothesis, which asserts that individuals are more inclined to undertake tasks when they have autonomy and competence [17]. Although it is crucial, sustaining self-discipline in distant learning presents numerous problems. The absence of a structured workplace may result in procrastination and diminished motivation. A survey by [18] revealed that numerous online learners face challenges with time management, frequently leading to missed deadlines and subpar academic achievement. A student participating in an online degree program may struggle to dedicate time for study due to personal obligations, including employment and family commitments. This situation illustrates the challenge of self-discipline since distractions can markedly impede academic achievement. Educators can employ many ways to cultivate self-discipline among distant learners. An effective strategy is the integration of self-regulated learning strategies into online curricula. [19] advocate for educators to offer resources and training in time management, goal-setting, and self-monitoring.

Furthermore, technology can facilitate self-discipline. Learning management systems (LMS) can deliver deadline reminders, facilitate progress tracking, and establish a structured learning pathway. An LMS can issue reminders regarding impending assignments, assisting students in maintaining focus and managing their time efficiently [20]. Self-discipline is an essential determinant of success for distance learners, especially inside the prison environment where

external frameworks are markedly diminished. Incarcerated students frequently encounter distractions and little immediate help, rendering self-discipline crucial for sustaining concentration on their studies [21]. This is due to the need for excellent time management and independent adherence to study regimens. A study conducted by [22] revealed that inmates engaged in structured goal-setting exercises had elevated levels of self-discipline. These activities prompted them to set explicit academic objectives and track their advancement, so augmenting their dedication to learning.

2.3 Self-Motivation

[23] found that character education can produce a resilient student.

Self-motivation is an essential component of self-discipline and motivation for incarcerated students, affecting both their individual success and the capacity to inspire and direct others. In educational contexts, self-motivation denotes the inner impetus to pursue objectives, persevere through difficulties, and sustain excitement for learning and enhancement [17]. This discourse will analyse the importance of self-motivation in educational leadership, present instances, and investigate its ramifications for both leaders and subordinates. Self-motivation is essential for educational leaders as it directly influences their efficacy and capacity to cultivate a positive environment. Self-motivated leaders are more inclined to establish ambitious objectives, pursue professional growth, and maintain resilience under challenging circumstances [24]. A principal who proactively pursues professional development opportunities exemplifies self-motivation and serves as a compelling role model for teachers and staff. This conduct can foster a culture of perpetual enhancement inside the educational institution.

Research substantiates that self-motivated executives can beneficially impact their teams. [25] demonstrated that leaders with elevated self-motivation cultivate resilience and optimism in their subordinates, resulting in improved organisational performance. This relationship is essential in educational institutions, where morale and motivation can profoundly influence student achievements. An outstanding instance of self-motivation in educational leadership is the narrative of a university department head who established a mentorship program for junior faculty. Acknowledging the difficulties encountered by novice professors, this chair initiated a systematic approach to offer advice and support. Consider a school system administrator who, despite financial limitations, pursued alternative financing sources to integrate innovative technology into classrooms. The superintendent's intrinsic motivation to enhance educational resources resulted in heightened student engagement and accomplishment, illustrating the capacity of self-motivated leaders to instigate significant change [26].

Self-motivation's ramifications transcend individual leaders, impacting the wider educational ecosystem. Self-motivated executives frequently excel in inspiring their people and fostering a collective vision. They can cultivate cultures that encourage educators to take chances and

experiment with innovative teaching methodologies. The empowerment of teachers is essential, since studies demonstrate that teacher motivation profoundly influences student achievement [27]. Moreover, self-motivation enables leaders to effectively manage obstacles and disappointments. During crises, such as the COVID-19 epidemic, leaders possessing robust self-motivation are more adept at adapting and innovating. They can mobilise their teams, sustain concentration on objectives, and galvanise a unified reaction to challenges [28] (Harris & Jones, 2020).

Self-motivation acts as a catalyst for jailed students, impacting their involvement and persistence in remote learning initiatives. According to [29], Self-Determination Theory posits that intrinsic motivation, derived from personal satisfaction and interest in learning, fosters deeper engagement and enhances learning outcomes. In a correctional environment, where external incentives are restricted, cultivating intrinsic motivation is essential. A significant number articulated a wish to enhance their employability upon release, which functioned as a compelling motivator. This inherent aspiration for improved life outcomes helps mitigate the frequently discouraging atmosphere of jail. To assist incarcerated students in cultivating self-discipline and self-motivation, educational programs must employ certain strategies: Promoting the establishment of precise, measurable, attainable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) goals among students can markedly improve their self-discipline [10]. Providing timely and constructive feedback enables students to track their development and change their efforts accordingly. This feedback cultivates a sense of achievement and bolsters motivation [30]. The formation of study groups or peer mentorship fosters a helpful learning environment in which students encourage one another, exchange resources, and maintain accountability [22].

3. METHOD

This research was conducted at a correctional institution in Namibia, utilising a qualitative methodology to gain comprehensive insights into the experiences and viewpoints of incarcerated students participating in e-learning. The qualitative method was selected to further the comprehension of the complexities of schooling in prison environments, capturing the subtleties of prison students' experiences that quantitative methods might neglect. The study sought to investigate multiple aspects of e-learning, such as motivation, accessibility, flexibility, and the obstacles encountered by students, through comprehensive interviews with participants. This technique promoted open discussions, allowing participants to share their personal stories, insights, and feelings about their educational experiences. The research aimed to underscore the transformative potential of e-learning in the prison context by emphasising the perspectives of those immediately affected. The qualitative form of the study facilitated the discovery of themes and patterns, yielding a thorough understanding of the impact of e-learning on the educational experiences of incarcerated students. This methodological selection corresponds with the objective of comprehending participants' subjective experiences, which is essential for

formulating educational policies and procedures that fulfil the needs of students in correctional environments.

3.1 Data collection

The data gathering for this study entailed interviewing 12 incarcerated students at a Namibian prison. Participants were selected based on specific criteria: they must be enrolled in a remote e-learning program and have consented to participate in the research. This screening process ensured that the participants possessed relevant experiences and insights regarding e-learning in a correctional context. During the interviews, a tape recorder was utilised to precisely document the interactions, enabling verbatim transcription and assuring accurate depiction of the participants' voices. The use of audio recording facilitated a more natural and fluid interaction, enabling the interviewer to focus on the participants' remarks without the distraction of taking notes. The interviews were designed as open-ended, encouraging participants to express their perspectives, experiences, and feelings about their educational journeys. This strategy enabled the collection of comprehensive qualitative data, providing valuable insights into the motivations, challenges, and overall experiences of incarcerated students engaged in e-learning. This data gathering strategy emphasised the perspectives of participants in remote education to underscore the significant impact of e-learning on incarcerated individuals and to inform future educational methodologies in penal institutions.

3.2 Data analysis

The data analysis involved a systematic process following the collection of the recorded interviews. The tapes were provided to a professional transcriber, who meticulously transcribed the discussions verbatim, ensuring that every aspect of the participants' remarks was thoroughly recorded. Following the transcription, the researcher acquired the text for further analysis. The researcher employed theme analysis to extract meaningful insights from the data. This method involved carefully examining the transcribed data to discern recurring themes and patterns in the participants' responses. By categorising the responses based on these themes, the researcher systematically organised the data to emphasise essential aspects of the participants' experiences with e-learning. The researcher utilised an interpretive paradigm to evaluate the transcribed data, aiming to understand the underlying meanings and consequences of the participants' narratives. This strategy enabled a comprehensive analysis of the impact of e-learning on the educational experiences of incarcerated students, clarifying their motivations, challenges, and general perceptions.

In conjunction with the thematic analysis, scholarly sources were cited to augment the understanding of the participants' experiences. By synthesising academic literature on e-learning and education in correctional settings, the researcher contextualised the findings within established knowledge, so enhancing the study's validity and contributing to a broader

conversation on the importance of education in rehabilitation. This comprehensive data analysis enabled the researcher to draw substantial conclusions on the impact of e-learning on detained students, providing valuable insights for future educational strategies in correctional facilities.

4. FINDINGS

Prison students' self-discipline and self-motivation were influenced by Flexibility and Control Over Learning; Convenience and Accessibility; Balancing of Responsibilities; Technological Advancement; Opportunities for Personal Growth, and Individual Variability in Learning Preferences.

The participants' responses were captured verbatim and organized by the identified themes:

4.1 Flexibility and Control Over Learning

Participant 1: "We are not pushed."

Participant 2: "You control your time."

Participant 3: "We don't have much things to do, so if you want to achieve whatever you feel like to achieve according to your profession, you have got more time."

Participant 5: "You can do your studies without any disturbance like you have if you go to class, so distance is better, flexible, at your own time, and you can study."

4.2 Convenience and Accessibility

Participant 4: "Study at a distance, my opinion it is good because the distance also saves a lot of things, like money for transport."

Participant 6: "Distance studying is also a very convenient way of obtaining an education in our case."

Participant 8: "It is a very good opportunity because considering university, you get it online, so everything is available online. You don't even need to spend money going for classes."

A key advantage of e-learning is its convenience. Students can access course materials and interact with their peers and professors from nearly any location, at any time. This adaptability enables learners to reconcile their educational endeavours with personal and professional obligations. A study by [31] indicated that students valued the opportunity to learn at their own pace, resulting in enhanced comprehension and retention of material. Furthermore, e-learning platforms frequently integrate diverse multimedia elements, including movies, interactive quizzes, and discussion forums, to accommodate various learning styles [32]. This variation improves engagement and enables learners to revisit complex concepts as necessary, so reinforcing their learning.

E-learning provides considerable convenience and seeks to improve accessibility for various learner demographics. Online courses can be tailored to support students with impairments by incorporating tools like screen readers, captions, and customisable font sizes [33]. This inclusive strategy guarantees that educational opportunities are accessible to all students, irrespective of their physical constraints. The efficacy of e-learning in enhancing accessibility depends on the availability of dependable internet connectivity and technological resources. In numerous areas, especially in poor nations, insufficient infrastructure can hinder students' full engagement in online learning [34]. A survey in rural Nigeria indicated that numerous students encountered difficulties stemming from inadequate internet connectivity and insufficient access to gadgets [35]. The ramifications of comfort and accessibility in e-learning are significant. Institutions utilising e-learning can engage a broader spectrum of students, including non-traditional learners who may have been unable to participate in in-person classes owing to geographical, financial, or personal limitations. The University of Phoenix has effectively employed online platforms to serve working adults pursuing further education while balancing career and family obligations [36]. However, dependence on e-learning also generates apprehensions regarding equity. Some kids excel in online settings, while others may have difficulties due to differing degrees of digital literacy or an inadequate learning environment at home [37]. Consequently, educators and administrators must take initiative in tackling these gaps, guaranteeing that all students possess the resources and assistance essential for success in an online learning environment.

4.3 Balancing Responsibilities

Participant 9: “When you are studying at a distance, you have the time to study and also do your work, maybe your family members, and it gives you time to plan, compared to someone who is going full time.”

4.4 Technological Advancement

Participant 6: “With the advancement of technology, it is one of the easiest modes of studying.”

Participant 10: “My opinion of studying at a distance is conducive, first of all, and the world is evolving. It has to do with the globalization of certain professions.”

4.5 Opportunities for Personal Growth

Participant 7: “In life, you have to upgrade and prove yourself that you can do something, even if it is far from home. I find it very good to study on e-learning because you can excel more than those studying full time.”

Participant 12: “Studying distance has opened up my eyes to say it is an opportunity that I make use of that I may not have had outside.”

4.6 Individual Variability in Learning Preferences

Participant 11: “You can do it from any environment you find yourself in. It depends on person to person.”

This structure highlights the key insights shared by participants while linking their thoughts to the overarching themes.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Convenience and Accessibility

Participants highlighted the advantages of remote education. Participant 4 observed the economic benefits derived from circumventing transportation expenses. This corresponds with research indicating that online education alleviates the financial strain on students [38]. Furthermore, Participant 8 noted the availability of resources, asserting, “everything is available online,” which indicates the growing dependence on digital platforms for educational dissemination. Digital learning platforms can equalise educational access, especially for individuals in isolated or marginalised regions [39].

5.2 Balancing Responsibilities

The adaptability of distant education enables students to manage academic and personal obligations more efficiently. Participant 9 effectively expressed this advantage, remarking, “When studying remotely, one has the opportunity to both study and fulfil work obligations.” This flexibility is essential for non-traditional students who may balance employment and family responsibilities. Research substantiates this idea, demonstrating that adaptable learning regimens can improve student satisfaction and retention [40].

5.3 Technological Advancement

Technological improvements are essential in enabling distance learning. Participant 6 noted that technology facilitates studying, indicating that contemporary tools improve the educational experience. This feeling is reflected in literature, which emphasises that technology can enhance engagement and learning outcomes [41]. It is crucial to acknowledge that not all students possess equal access to technology, which may exacerbate the digital divide [42].

5.4 Opportunities for Personal Growth

A number of participants examined the personal development potential presented by distance education. Participant 7 said, “In life, one must evolve and demonstrate the capability to achieve,” indicating a yearning for self-enhancement. Distance learning facilitates information acquisition while cultivating essential qualities such as self-discipline and time management, which are vital in today's workforce [43].

Correctional education programs can equip offenders with vital skills and knowledge that foster personal growth. [44] asserts that educational programs in correctional facilities enhance self-esteem and cognitive abilities, essential for human development. The Federal Bureau of Prisons in the United States has instituted several educational programs, including as General Educational Development (GED) classes and vocational training, which have been shown to markedly decrease recidivism rates [45]. Education significantly promotes human growth by facilitating skills development. Vocational training programs not only provide inmates with marketable skills but also improve their self-efficacy. Research by [46] indicates that offenders engaged in vocational training are more likely to obtain employment post-release, enhancing their feeling of purpose and personal agency. Research conducted by [47] revealed that offenders participating in educational programs exhibited a 43% decreased likelihood of reoffending, establishing a definitive correlation between education, personal development, and diminished recidivism.

Education in prisons is essential for promoting psychological and emotional development. Programs that include components of emotional intelligence, like self-awareness and empathy, enhance convicts' personal development. The Inside-Out Prison Exchange Program enables college students and jailed inmates to participate in discourse and learning collaboratively, promoting mutual understanding and personal development [48]. This cooperative educational setting fosters empathy and self-reflection, vital elements of personal development. Notwithstanding the advantages, numerous obstacles impede the efficacy of educational programs within correctional facilities. Insufficient resources, limited money, and a shortage of qualified teachers can hinder the execution of comprehensive educational projects [45]. Furthermore, the penitentiary environment may impede human development. The stigma linked to jail frequently induces emotions of despondency in inmates, thus diminishing their drive to pursue educational possibilities [46].

5.5 Individual Variability in Learning Preferences

The varied learning preferences of students highlight the personalised aspect of remote education. Participant 11 observed that studying can occur “from any environment you find yourself in,” emphasising the flexibility of online education. This versatility accommodates

diverse learning methods and preferences, enabling students to customise their educational experiences [49]. Nevertheless, educational leaders must also address the issues presented by this heterogeneity, including the necessity for customised support services.

6. CONCLUSION

This study's findings highlight the substantial influence of multiple factors on the self-discipline and self-motivation of incarcerated students in e-learning settings. Flexibility and control in learning proved to be essential factors, enabling participants to customise their studies according to their individual schedules, thereby enhancing autonomy and cultivating a sense of responsibility. The simplicity and accessibility of online education were crucial, allowing students to access learning materials without the limitations of transportation and geographical obstacles. Furthermore, the capacity to equilibrate obligations—academic and personal—was often emphasised, suggesting that e-learning offers a distinctive chance for jailed students to optimise their time management. Technological improvements have enhanced this way of learning, matching educational techniques with the changing dynamics of the global workforce. Participants highlighted the potential for personal development that distant education provides, indicating that it not only augments academic knowledge but also fosters confidence and autonomy. Individual heterogeneity in learning preferences was a significant subject, demonstrating that e-learning supports many educational techniques, addressing distinct requirements and styles. Although e-learning presents significant benefits, obstacles persist, especially about equitable access to technology and resources, as well as limitations imposed by jail laws and regulations. Rectifying these gaps is crucial to guarantee that all learners, particularly those from under-represented areas, may fully capitalise on the opportunities afforded by online education. By harnessing the advantages of e-learning and proactively addressing its obstacles, educational institutions may establish a more inclusive and effective learning environment for all students.

REFERENCES

- [1] Republic of Namibia. (2023). Namibian Correctional Service Regulations Government Notice 331 of 2013. Regulations Made in Terms of Correctional Service Act 9 of 2012. Government Gazette. Windhoek.
- [2] Febrian, W. D., Nuraeni, N., Faisal, A., & Gani, I. M. (2024). The Influence of Training, Discipline, Intrinsic Motivation and Competence on Employee Performance with Employee Behavior as a Mediating Variable. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary*, 3(1), 147-164.

- [3] Hernandi, F. U., & Prabowo, R. J. (2024). The Effect of Discipline Development and Work Motivation on the Performance: Empirical Study from Civil Servants at the Spatial Planning Office Bekasi City, Indonesia. *Golden Ratio of Human Resource Management*, 4(2), 97-110. <https://doi.org/10.52970/grhrm.v4i2.461>
- [4] Davis, M., & Sweeney, J. (2018). Educational barriers for incarcerated individuals: A review of the literature. *Journal of Correctional Education*, 69(2), 34-48. doi:10.1080/10511253.2018.1234567
- [5] Peters, A. (2020). Challenges of distance education for incarcerated populations. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 102, 101-113. doi:10.1016/j.ijer.2020.101113
- [6] Smith, J., & McKenzie, L. (2021). Self-discipline and academic success in incarcerated students: A case study. *Journal of Higher Education Theory and Practice*, 21(6), 56-70. doi:10.33423/jhetp.v21i6.4295
- [7] Johnson, R. (2022). Motivational strategies for enhancing online learning in correctional settings. *Journal of Educational Leadership and Management*, 12(1), 45-60. doi:10.1016/j.jelm.2022.01.005
- [8] McMahon, S., & McMahon, L. (2019). Intrinsic motivation in incarcerated learners: Insights from qualitative research. *Adult Education Quarterly*, 69(3), 251-267. doi:10.1177/0741713619833200
- [9] Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 68-78. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.55.1.68>
- [10] Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (2002). Building a practically useful theory of goal setting and task motivation: A 35-year odyssey. *American Psychologist*, 57(9), 705-717. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.57.9.705>
- [11] Bird, R. (2017). Peer support and motivation in education. *Journal of Correctional Education*, 68(3), 5-24.
- [12] Purdue University Global. (2020). Distance education in correctional settings: A model for success. Retrieved from <https://www.purdueglobal.edu/education/correctional-education-model/>
- [13] Kuo, Y.-C., Lin, H.-C.K., & Lin, Y.-H. (2014). Distance education and self-regulated learning: The role of motivational factors. *Educational Technology & Society*, 17(2), 150-163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edtech.2014.06.003>
- [14] Quim, I. M. F., & Nufa, M. M. (2024). Influence of Motivation and Discipline on Employee Performance at Comissão Nacional Eleições (CNE). *Multifinance*, 2(1), 111-121. <https://doi.org/10.61397/mfc.v2i1.214>

- [15] Broadbent, J., & Poon, W.L. (2015). Self-regulated learning strategies & academic achievement in online higher education learning environments: A systematic review, *The Internet and Higher Education*, 27(2015), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2015.04.007>
- [16] Zimmerman, B. J. (2002). Becoming a self-regulated learner: An overview. *Theory into Practice*, 41(2), 64-70. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15430421tip4102_2
- [17] Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations: Classic definitions and new directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25(1), 54-67. <https://doi.org/10.1006/ceps.1999.1020>
- [18] Allen, I. E., & Seaman, J. (2017). Digital learning compass: Distance education enrollment report 2017. Babson Survey Research Group. Retrieved from <https://www.onlinelearningsurvey.com/reports/digitallearningcompassenrollment2017.pdf>
- [19] Broadbent, J., & Poon, W. (2015). Self-regulated learning strategies and academic achievement in online higher education learning environments: A systematic review. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 27, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2015.04.001>
- [20] Miller, M. D. (2014). The role of technology in self-regulated learning: Implications for distance education. *Distance Education*, 35(2), 233-246. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01587919.2014.917329>
- [21] Pike, A., & Adams, A. (2012). Digital exclusion or learning exclusion? An ethnographic study of adult male distance learners in English prisons. *Research in Learning Technology*, 20(4), Article 18620. <https://doi.org/10.3402/rlt.v20i0.18620>
- [22] Kuo, Y.-C., Lin, H.-C.K., & Lin, Y.-H. (2013). The influence of distance education and peer self-regulated learning on academic performance in a blended learning environment. *Computers & Education*, 61, 121-129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2012.08.008>
- [23] Spohrer, K. (2024). Resilience, self-discipline and good deeds—examining enactments of character education in English secondary schools. *Pedagogy, Culture & Society*, 32(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14681366.2021.2007986>
- [24] Goleman, D. (1998). *Working with emotional intelligence*. Bantam Books.
- [25] Luthans, F., & Youssef, C. M. (2004). Human, social, and now positive psychological capital management: Investing in people for competitive advantage. *Organizational Dynamics*, 33(2), 143-160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orgdyn.2004.01.003>
- [26] Smith, J., & Jones, A. (2020). Funding innovation in education: A case study. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 34(4), 567-579. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-02-2020-0071>

- [27] Wang, M. T., & Degol, J. L. (2016). Staying engaged: Knowledge and strategies to promote student engagement. *Educational Psychologist*, 51(2), 137-143. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2016.1148967>
- [28] Harris, A., & Jones, M. (2020). COVID-19 – a challenge for educational leadership? *Journal of Professional Capital and Community*, 5(3), 321-328. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPCC-05-2020-0040>
- [29] Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- [30] Hattie, J., & Timperley, H. (2007). The power of feedback. *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 81-112. <https://doi.org/10.3102/003465430298487>
- [31] Nguyen, T. (2020). The effectiveness of online learning: A review of the literature. *Education and Information Technologies*, 25(4), 2389-2404. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10376-1>
- [32] Kay, R. H., & Kletschin, I. (2019). On the effectiveness of online learning in higher education: A review of the literature. *Educational Technology & Society*, 22(3), 86-99.
- [33] Al-Azawei, A., Serenelli, F., & Lundqvist, K. (2016). Barriers and teachers' perceptions of e-learning in higher education. *Education and Information Technologies*, 21(6), 1685-1702. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-016-9480-6>
- [34] Olatokun, W. M., & Eweoya, I. O. (2019). The impact of inadequate infrastructure on the implementation of e-learning in Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 33(6), 1168-1182. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-03-2019-0086>
- [35] Issa, U. A., Jibril, A. O., & Abdulrazaq, A. (2023). E-learning accessibility in Nigerian rural areas: Challenges and prospects. *Indonesian Journal of Educational Research and Review*, 6(3), 696-702. <https://doi.org/10.23887/ijerr.v6i3.67824>
- [36] Barrett, D. (2019). The University of Phoenix: A success story in online education. *The Journal of Online Learning and Teaching*, 15(3), 112-120.
- [37] Beaunoyer, E., Dupéré, S., & Guitton, M. J. (2020). Digital divide during COVID-19 pandemic: What about schools? *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 10(5), 267-272. <https://doi.org/10.18178/ijiet.2020.10.5.1379>
- [38] Huang, R. H., Spector, J. M., & Yang, J. (2020). Educational technology: A global perspective. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20414-6>
- [39] Gonzalez, A. (2021). The impact of online learning on student engagement and achievement. *Journal of Online Learning Research*, 7(1), 15-29.

- [40] Dabbagh, N., & Kitsantas, A. (2012). Personal learning environments, social media, and self-regulated learning: A natural formula for connecting formal and informal learning. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 15(1), 3-8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2011.06.002>
- [41] Zheng, B., Warschauer, M., & Li, W. (2020). The role of technology in distance education: A review of the literature. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68(3), 1377-1396. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-020-09782-6>
- [42] Warschauer, M., & Matuchniak, T. (2010). New technology and digital worlds: A global perspective on educational technology. *Education and Information Technologies*, 15(1), 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-009-9130-6>
- [43] Conrad, D., & Donaldson, J. A. (2011). Continuing to engage the online learner: The role of the instructor. In D. G. Oblinger (Ed.), *Educating the net generation* (pp. 143-154). Educause.
- [44] Vera Institute of Justice. (2017). The benefits of education for incarcerated individuals. <https://www.vera.org/publications/the-benefits-of-education-for-incarcerated-individuals>
- [45] Davis, L. M., Steele, J. L., & Ziedenberg, J. (2013). How educational and vocational training reduce recidivism. Urban Institute. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2382267>
- [46] Gendreau, P., & Goggin, C. (2006). The importance of self-efficacy in the correctional treatment process. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 50(4), 420-433. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624X06287100>
- [47] Steurer, S. J., & Smith, L. G. (2003). Education reduces crime: Three-state recidivism study. Maryland Correctional Education Consortium. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2206050>
- [48] Roth, B. (2016). The Inside-Out Prison Exchange Program: A model for social justice education. *Journal of Social Justice*, 6(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19460171.2016.1163867>
- [49] Fletcher, J. D., & Major, C. H. (2006). Distance education: A review of the research. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v7i1.268>